

Sociology of the Seventieth Culture from Nasiriyah to Europe, Aqeel Ali and Kamal Sabti as a Selection

Ali Hashim Talab Al Zireijawy

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 03, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: August 02, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Sociology, Nasiriyah, Linguistic</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4210628</p>	<p><i>The city of Nasiriyah is distinguished by an intellectual and civilizational heritage that its children can voluntarily educate in, intermingling with many cultures, some of which are descended from the oldest human civilizations. Societal culture varies, and there is no doubt about that, as literature and art are the image of life in which human thought is reflected throughout the ages. The city continued to weave its literature into poetry tales, and poetry was a craft that poets master, as it is the argument and evidence of the ingenuity of the narrator's personality, and the means by which people hang around in literary circles at times, and comic at other times. Seminars were formed in the city after World War II and seminars benefited writers and intellectuals (2), including the seminars held by the poet Abbas Al-Mulla Ali, who used to deliver linguistic and logical lectures to his disciples, and he taught them poetry and essay writing. One night of a week was devoted to the students to disclose the poetry and prose they were assigned to, then followed by a new lesson in language and logic. (3). The café (Azran Al-Badri) Okaz Al-Madinah and Marbad were its glory, in which its writers were competing, and it is not surprising that the legal judge of the city was among its visitors (4). Dwelling with love, and sleeping on the harshness of life and wishes in a walled city with the incense of dreams) (5). Poetry, art and other literature met with acceptance among the people of the city first, then it found its echo outside the borders of the great homeland secondly, so the literature moved to the global environment, and began to wear the uniform of global culture that investigates conditions and features higher than the conditions and features of the local environment, and perhaps the intellectual currents in its environment were denied. The general public is a reason behind its displacement to the global environment, so the city of Nasiriyah continued to give birth to many generations of writers, whose chain was not interrupted even in its darkest and poor days, as its impact was evident in the seventies generation of Iraqi poets. As it was an environmental incubator for the late poets Aqil Ali and Kamal Sabti, just as it was an incubator for the various literary arts. The research will focus on the social and environmental factors that contributed to the alienation of the poets, whether it was spatial or psychological alienation.</i></p>

1. Introduction

Self-affliction and alienation in Aqil Ali's poetry:

Aqil Ali was born in the city of Nasiriyah in 1949, and he was from an educated social milieu, but he suffers from hardship and poverty ((and he still lives in it, a baker, dividing his time between writing poetry and practicing manual work)) (6), and the economic conditions were He cast a perversion on poets and writers, so Aqil Ali traveled to Oman seeking livelihood, freedom and serenity, after his livelihood narrowed, and he found no other way but to leave from a realistic childish origin to another unknown, as he says:

This is a country we abandoned. We abandoned its stones

They are stumpy throats, they are tired men

Except that and I push her away

Hopefully, charm maps

I approach madness, and incite him. Send rocks and wait ... (7)

The beautiful things have been transformed by the poet after he hated life and the place he was familiar with, that is, the aesthetic presence faded before his eyes as he struggled between the heart of a lover and the last stoner of this place that he was familiar with, as the stoning has two connotations, the first of which is desertion

without return, and the second is the devilish place - may What is meant is a wide spatial area - after every beautiful loved one died, and its true connotation changed. And by that, he unites the two selves, the one with the dead waterwheel (river), and the same who died when he decided to leave his city, his friends and his memories. It is easy to glimpse the link between the meanings)) (8), the psychological turmoil made the poet unrepentant, but rather he was relegated to a departed from psychological alienation, to find himself a true alienation.

The dominance of the cultural scene in the city of Nasiriyah influenced the state of its writers with one another, and perhaps some of them were educating each other, or being a student, for Aqil Ali was responsible for the perfection of my sabbatical ((on a poem that may not have been grilled with maturity of bread)) (9), though It belongs to a different direction, because Aqeel Ali belongs to the modern day brats, Jan Damo, Abdul Latif Al-Rashed, Kazar Hantoush, Hadi Al-Sayed, Sabah Al-Gharawi and others. Aqeel's misfortune was not imposed on him, but rather it was an optional tort that reflects an intellectual philosophy. It is prominent in the world cultures in which the great Tramps inherited the modern era (Baudelaire, Rambo, Albu Denmar, the philosopher Sartre) and it is an important phenomenon in literature that contributes to raising it above the bourgeoisie and the career-killing killing of talent (11). We cannot deny the poet's intellectual inclination to cling to his poetry, prompted by a set of reasons, including the nature of the prevailing culture in the eighties and nineties, the poets' intrusion into narrow fields of poetry, and the financial need that fell on the shoulders of the Southerners, which prompted him to choose an exile for him by his own will, so he deserted Nasserism To Baghdad, where he lived the life of the exiles and went to the oldest of its features, Rashid Street, Haydar Khanna and Kadhimiya Street, and chose the (Diamond) Hotel in the middle of Rasheed Street as his home. Men of power-seeking praise of the ruler. The expression of his apology was extended, and the poet decided that he should be silent, and that silence would be a trust that he carried, until he was called the silent poet (12).

The poet suffered the bitterness of alienation and distancing from the homeland, but with the severity of his suffering from the spatial alienation, he lived and felt an alienation of another kind while he was inside his homeland and among his fellow countrymen, which is the spiritual and psychological alienation as a result of his suffering from the harsh conditions he went through (13). The misery and misery and the series of intellectual harassments that he suffered caused silence and failure to rise to a state that ends the cruelty of suffering, which inherited to him a state of intellectual impotence and despair from life, as his self is squeezed in a terrible cycle of spiritual alienation (14), but he soon sent his groans and regrets And his pain prevailed over the same stranger, sad, rebellious, revealing what surrounds him, saying:

This is how I began my ascent

My soul for monsters was suspended like an amulet

This is how I started my walk to the climax

Boats are packed with locusts, and the letters on the hills wash their heads

Ah well ... ah well

To awaken this star, let us untie the bridle of our bliss

The call to freedom and not to surrender has become an inevitable process for the poet after he tried silence and reached an imperative unleash his emotions and portrayed them in many ways, which were still being interpreted in terms of his feeling or not the situations he was going through, and there is no way out but delinquency to turmoil and anxiety, Which led him to the modernist rationalist discourse as "He deals with the other consciously and cautiously, takes from him and leaves, quotes and discards, fits and reconciles, and adds, changes or fabricates, relying on all this to his authentic, established standards and values" (16). The tools he worked on and his language were tight and cautious, and the reasons for caution were known to everyone in an intellectually exhausted atmosphere that did not allow him ((the possibility to have a personal self-awareness, that is, to have a subjective vision of reality, stemming primarily from his own feelings and suffering)) (17) , The conversation seemed to symbolize the desire to enter another world in order to achieve his goals in a dangerous journey, but hope is tied to the idea of self-change that he leads wherever he goes, and the search for another society that suits his aspirations, ideas and emotions, because such a level was not prepared to appear It is evident in a society suffering from intellectual and social repression and submission to the conditions that accompany its environment and the state that surrounds it. And in spite of that, his poem was overflowing with signs and replete with symbols that suggest the fingerprints of time and predict the recent history ((a model that defines for us the historical (near) dimension of emotional meanings. That remained inherent in the life of this person, so he expressed his history, existence and reality in poetry, and within this poetry all emerge. The overlapping meanings, and the subtle particles that surrounded this life, so his poetry was a document, and his feeling was a picture, and his suffering was a painting of the paintings of history)) (18), which was crowned with emotions and emotional charges flowing in the medium through which the human forms that the poet wanted to express (19).

The impact of the cruelty of life was evident in Aqeel Ali's poetry, just as the trawl contributed to the distinction of his poems (((Upon reading them at first glance, with their special features and their dramatic dimensions,

language and technique), and with their bold equation between the contradictions, a poetry that raises surprise and confuses any previously proposed critical tools, and Aqeel's poetic language contains a lot of Strangers also, poems that put themselves thus before the reader are difficult, enigmatic, enveloped in mystery, and hostile to hidden worlds that have no calendar)) (20), as saying:

What other than the wreckage of poems will be caught

The earth does not give its traps, and the pitchfork of the night puts on its garments

That is the begging sign, those are evidence of persecution.

Do not ignite other than the reality of the look. (21)

Everything is unfamiliar. He broke the restrictions and barriers and came with a poetic image in a way that wanted him to bring the stranger and did not establish in the mind of the recipient and his taste other than the possibility of Ali's mind and his strangeness, that is, the poem breaks out through the transgressions it presents that do not extend to real realism or poetry in any way. The recipient finds difficulty in the meaning of the poem, which may disturb him in the search ((Rather, it is expected that her treasures will be presented to him with complete ease, as they are not carried to him, but the meaning is clear, easy, and comfortable)) (22), and this is what was not present in the most general of 5he poems of Aqil Ali, which the recipient needs to search for, critical culture and linguistic knowledge, This is because the poet has broken and confused the features of reality within the text, and thus the recipient will not always succeed in finding the true meaning except by the mediation of the biographical fallacy when the reader moves in search of matching the reality of the text and the poet (23), in line with modern linguistics in its study of the changes of meaning, which puts In the first place the psychological nature. It is also two large paradigms across parity and transcendence (24). The poet suffered indifference and deliberate marginalization of him, whether he was from his countrymen or Arab critics, except for some fair ones. The Moroccan King invited him to visit Morocco, and to send a media delegation to meet him (26), while the writers of Iraq and his intellectuals looked at the poet with suspicion and suspicion, so they judged his appearance sometimes, and his alcoholic imbalance at other times. His silence and emptiness were to the world of the subconscious, and his lack of boast, and he stole the attention of those working in the literary arena.

And if we were not from the two generations of the poet, or from those who had met him, then we are referring to an accurate method, and we seek accuracy in responding to what was rumored about him, and we do not repeat what our ancestors said about pre-Islamic poetry altogether, and if what the Arabs said at the time was made and turned on them, the said ones will not be asked With this themselves, why didn't the bee-haired do that for himself? Was there in ancient Arab times a name of a poet? Why did not one poet mention what he did in the poetry of his majors? And we would like to say: Why did the maker of Aqil's poetry not attribute the poetry to himself? Is the popularity, popularity and deliberation of the collections of Aqeel Ali, something that Adib does not like for himself? As for the mastery of singing, this is something that has existed since Arabic poetry was found. And the most prominent poets used to tell them for a reason. The research argues that questioning the ability and proficiency of some poets will remain an inherent characteristic from the pre-Islamic era to beyond this generation, without the existence of mental evidence that can be referred to and presented convincingly to the recipient, but rather the return of everyone in judging this insult to be made and turned.

It seems that Aqeel Ali was aware of what was going on around him in terms of whispering and winking, but he did not care about that, as he did not ask for prestige or wealth in his poetry, and he was very confident that time is sufficient to raise the injustice and restore the truth to him, then he was not concerned with what others say and he thought that their argument He opened a dialogue with him that cost him his betrayal, and he sees that they know who he is, so he says: ((Nothing justifies the betrayal of silence, they know very well who Aqeel Ali is)), (28) Then he addresses his question to his closest friends, who are the most sincere of them, and asks him, And a requirement for him, not to touch the faithfulness of his silence ((You wrote about me once with neutrality, will you write about me after my death? ... And will you do justice to me?)) (29).

The fame that the poet acquired was its first space in Europe, as they found in the poetry of Aqil Ali their intention, so his collections were a field of extensive research and study in different and ancient schools of criticism and thought. And the demand for his poetry (Janan Adam) was increasing outside his native Iraq, if the court was printed and distributed in the countries of the Arab world (31). And they change him publicly sometimes, as Saadi Yusef Aqeel Ali sought permission ((to borrow some of his stunned poetic phrases to include them in his new poetry)) (32). Also, his collection, Adam's Gardens in it ((an exceptional poetic effort in the history of the Iraqi poem, and that is associated with the most important experiences of global achievement)) (33) But what is in the hands of Arab researchers and critics was not balanced by critical studies except rarely, despite the poet's indifference to criticism. As Aqil Ali advised him while addressing a writer advising him: ((Do not pay much attention to criticism, good poetry is not taken as good poetry as authentic skilled people know from afar, say your word freely and go)) (34), but we do not fail to find someone who has informed by saying Quick criticism he administered on Aqeel Ali's poetry, and he found that his texts ((You do not want to teach us or benefit us with anything as much as you want to suggest through non-indicative words)) (35), and in

that he is like the modern European poet. If we look closely at the poetry of the Europeans, we find some techniques of Aqil Ali embedded in the structure of their poetic texts to connect and tension between the contradictions, which is also an ancient European philosophical idea that goes back to Aristotle, Goethe and their predecessors (36).

1. The sociology of self-culture and its alienation in the poetry of Kamal Sabti:

Poet Kamal Sabti was more fortunate than his colleague, as he tried to empty some of his harshness in a newspaper column that he was editing in Al-Qadisiyah newspaper when he joined the military service, in addition to his work in the cultural section of Radio Baghdad in the eighties, and his birth was on 7/28/1955 in the city Nasiriyah (37), and he used to live a private life, and he was not organizing his life, as he only owned an imaginary bed with which he traveled in many places alternating between the internal departments (the chic) during his studies at the Institute of Fine Arts and among friends' homes during his membership in the Writers Union and his performance of compulsory service. In view of all this, he may write poetry or sometimes recite it (38), and he embodied that alienation in his life, saying: (39).

*Dust is falling near the Children's Lake.
The poets are going to the nearby road
That was the sky
The singer said
So, I woke up in bed
Its limbs were the bars of a prison called Dream
In the dictionary of the poor*

The poet lived his life of internal alienation, as utopia was the expressive means of him to enter into a life other than the one he lives, as his bed was attached to him even in his dreams, and this alienation we notice through his emotions and images ((Because every poetry is unlimited pictorial flows, and emotional movements An unconsciousness comes at a moment when the poet is absent from his sensual reality.

It seems that the most influential situation in the poet's life is his failure in the Academy of Fine Arts, although the poet was one of the first students in the Institute of Fine Arts that qualified him for admission to the Academy of Fine Arts, Department of Cinema (41), and this matter generated great pain in his heart that made him sad and desperate. In addition to his condition that he was suffering from due to his spatial and psychological alienation, as he says: (42).

*Here you are, you alone, you finished here
Wandering sad, she asks the prophets
About your brutal hemorrhage, about a cry
A mountain like a mountain:
Mysterious poet's blood
You ask, O transgressor:
Who passed this evening?
And you are still
Wandering, sad, the prophets prophesy
Mysterious poet's blood*

I, the poet, seem to surrender clearly to the logic of sadness and its changes expressed in the pronoun (you), as well as to the interrogative tools used in the text that spread confusion and to a question in a direct manner (here you alone, who passed this evening), so we notice the helplessness and surrender that the poet himself was responding to the call of Melancholy ((He responds to a greater extent than his first response to the ability of a printer that has the character of sadness and darkness, to the call of nature as a society, laws, pressure and blockade factors, so his disease becomes emotional depression, it is the poet's environment then, and he is in the midst of the poet then, and it is the poet's emotion about what is around him)) (43), so he decided his matter To leave his homeland and his childhood and chose to be a stranger, and his emotions embodied that decision that corresponds psychologically to the pain, sorrow and alienation he was familiar with, saying: (44).

*Then we may be without ships,
And we say: The roads are lost,
Near you, I hear its bells,
It is between your palms. Guide the one who cannot see,
A door will open,
Mountains will fall,
And warn her what the drums have recounted (44)*

The spirit of defiance was evident in the poet's emotions, despite the circumstances surrounding him previously, for there is something that he did not declare, and those spaces are only consecration of emotion that he did not reveal, and that this punctuation in order to avoid something that will happen, leaving the recipient to fill those blanks in the future while suggesting to him. To be aware of what the self has reached by not disclosing directly and losing the ways that he must become familiar with, since impotence, surrender and cultural alienation finds its way to him in every time and place, which generates alienation, i.e. mental disorder that makes it between existence and non-existence or, more precisely, a state ((loss of consciousness and paralysis) Mental powers or senses, or their deficiencies)) (45).

The story of Kamal Sabti's escape had expressed the personality and circumstances of this poet, as the delegation was scheduled to leave on September 7 and accompanied by five people, but he left the fisherman's hotel at night because of his debts to the hotel owner that weighed on his shoulders and could not pay them, in addition to what he was planning to travel before the delegation and leaving Finally (46) from his home secretly, he carries the factors of fear and hope, fear of the unknown and what the spatial alienation can carry away from the city, friends and their memories, and the hope of living away from intellectual and cultural oppression and obtaining a material return through which he can spread the thoughts and positions that emotions and emotions in him.

He went to European countries from Cyprus, where he did not find himself despite his contact with the poet Mahmoud Darwish, who secured this connection to the Lebanese poet Sabah Zwain, but the two could not achieve what Kemal Sabti had achieved, then he traveled to Yugoslavia and obtained political asylum in the mediation of the Nations After a period of time, he made Spain the important station of his life, as he married a literary activist and a professor at the University of Madrid called Maria, in addition to studying literature and philosophy at the Independent College, and he did not succeed in his marriage or childbearing, so he separated from his wife in 1997 (47 The research finds that the poet was haunted by Utopia (Iraq), Thus, he was a stranger, who suffered from emotional and emotional instability with his wife, but even with the university residence in which he was, for the spatial, psychological and social alienation compounded the poet and was the reason for his separation from his wife, as he says:

Our strangers from this wage ...

Strangers from this sleep ...

*Strangers from strangers exchanged frost with singing,
from right to left ...*

Arabs are full of singing,

And I celebrate the inheritance of remorse ...

Words do not come from words ... (48)

Nostalgia returned to the poet's soul and he could not adapt or live in an atmosphere that he was not familiar with or chose for himself, as he changed (warmth in cold, sun in rain, Iraq with alienation, and hope in remorse). For the reality that he was familiar with, and this is completely true with the literati's view of the place in the literary work, as it is based on the basis of ("from pure imagination, but it does not acquire its epics, its importance and even its permanence, if it is not identical to one degree or another with the world outside the text ...Moreover, the place conveys the sense of the meaning of life, and the emphasis is doubled on its continuity and extension. () (49), so space in poetry is not just a physical ground containing purely geometric formations, shapes and spaces, but it is also a psychological space that penetrates into the functional image and permeates it, in a way that gives it Psychological, geographical and social identity, that is, it gives it creative privacy) (50).

After that, the poet chose to be a true stranger as he traveled to the Netherlands and was alone except for some Arab brothers, and he could not break the restrictions of his unity and estrangement except for some trips he made to Sweden, America and London to visit and attend some conferences (51), and another group was issued to him (others. Before this time) in 2002 from Damascus, then (urgent mail for the dead) in the Netherlands in 2004, and finally (Sabra said the Four Natures) at Dar Al-Jamal in Germany in 2006 (52).

Kamal Sabti tried to remain connected to the Iraqi cultural scene despite the interruption of communication with him, and Megayluh regretted his distance, as his shadow remained present in Baghdad's literary markets (the Sayyad Hotel, Hasan Ajami Café, Parliament Café, and the Writers Union) and he had those who did not prolong. The visit to Hassan Ajami Café did not and will not be a poet and a literary man (53).

He was not disguised by the children of his generation and his adherents, and he was known for his care of poetic talents and providing assistance to them, as he used to deal professionally with the language and possessed its tools and dive into coding it, impressing his followers, and this enabled him to avoid his anxiety in festivals and celebrations of what was less and more, as it was the shortest poem of his share. It did not take a quarter of a minute (54).

The poet's relationship with his males, their courtship, his poetic standing among them, and the nature of his life and his abhorrence of restriction made a group of writers, poets and writers attracted around him and called him

the most beautiful titles. (57), (and Abu Al-Saud) (58), (and the poet of the sea rose) (59), (and the owner of the lake of children) (60), (and the poet of al-Qubiyah) (61).

He translated the poetry of Kamal Sabti into different languages ((As it was selected in Modern Arabic Poetry an anthology, issued by: Colombia University Press New York, 1987 and edited by a number of Arabists and specialists under the supervision of the critic Salma Al-Khadra Al-Jayyousi)) (62).He also translated the collection of (The Last of the Holy Cities) and various poems from the collections (The Sea Rose, Something remained, Hakim Without Cities, and a Museum of the Remnants of the Family), in addition to Professor Pedro Martin Montbith's translation of the poem (Royal Boats) from the Divan of Hakim Without Cities (63), Which was like a narrative dialogue in the style of (the ego) modern that tries to approach the receiver despite the ambiguity that accompanies the modern poem, as ((I adopt focused dialogue and moving away from the tone of narration, and pursuing the parts that contribute to building the narrative event)) (64), With diversity in self-expression and interrogation with multiple tools, saying:

I'm in the old house, and where would you be?

I'm at the old bar, and where would you be?

Be in me ... and I have pottery statues going down

Every time you ask the cities near and far:

Did you give us life?

Cities near and far were not answering, to us

Anagram !! What do you mean ? Clay,

the damage. And the wall of the brothel ... Where is alliteration?

We have hidden statues: The city has not yet given birth to the city

Her news continues to come to us: The soul is like deception

And the smoke is evidence of Mbeghana, she waited: a child asked her boats (65)

The poem had a global presence that showed the potential of Sabbatarian perfection in diversity and dealing with modernity in a manner of dialogue close to the recipient, which does not stray far from the global modernist achievement as its tools were close to clarity, especially in the use of interrogative tools that make the recipient tied to the poem continuously, because the change in Narrative dialogue may occur at any moment, in addition to the fact that it relies on religious and historical references in its constructive and content composition, such as his saying: ((Take the book with strength)) (66) when he resorted to the Almighty saying: (O long live, take the book with strength and give it wisdom) (67)), As well as the words Zamzam, the whale, the talisman, and the liturgy (68), which made the poem richer, more widely circulated and more common than his other poems. We notice in the poetry of Kamal Sebti many religious, literary, ideological, mythological, popular and historical references on which he leans on for the richness of his poetic experience as a result of his representation of many experiences related to persons, events and places which are (()) things capable of creating new situations that enhance the poet's production in line with his vision in his revival of the past when He considers it appropriate for his purpose) ((69) as we find (the kingdom, the Mass, the names of God, Zamzam, the book, the whale, the fire, the isthmus, the Adam's apple, the jinn, the tree trunk, the churches, Socrates, Plato, Al-Thaalabi, Ibn Rushd, the Euphrates, and the Marquis , Athens, Marrakech, and Cekor, an Egyptian city, the Mughals, Wellson, Mirabeau Bridge, the pagan temple, the Attarin mosque, and the Pharaonic tombs) (70).), As he employed it in proportion to the style of ((external or reference intertextuality)) (71), which occurs poetic clear in the texts because of its development, heart and transformation (72). This is what we did not find with Aqeel Ali, who did not base his style on any other references, and his language was difficult and his image was innovative and new.

Sabti's perfection was not inferior to his predecessor, as the incandescent flame of love and poetry was his constant beacon, in which he diversified his product, as his last years filled poetry, literary writings and cultural articles, and the field of poetry was the most fertile, as he looked and organized until he advanced (((With the modern poem to a wide range of affairs he did not notice) To it previously Iraqi poetry)) (73), and after developing the Arabic poem and introducing it to modernist universality, it was an anomaly to the poets of his seventy generation ((He used to share with them that impulse that would incite subsequent generations to return new areas, but his poetic performance was predicting that it is permissible, contrary to his peers. Tools that will enable him to continue)) (74).

He did not remain silent, and he was uniquely accomplished and was positioned in his poetic work to form a platform in which the space in which to grow and enrich him, and in which he excelled with his ferocity on the map of Iraqi and Arab poetry (75), the emergence of poetic abundance in his exile was a natural result, and a logical response to the retention that was narrowing Accordingly, his new theses, emigration and estrangement represented the maturity and sophistication that his poetic achievement reached in his fifth collection, and he announced his new theories and boycotted poetry in his sense at the time, since he released his fourth collection in 1989 (Museum of the Remains of the Family) (76).

It seems that the poet's way of living and caring for poetry for the sake of poetry, and escaping from life reality to beyond consciousness, we have lost a lot of his poetry, and it is no wonder that modern day poets do not disclose everything they say, and in that they envisage various things that they do not reveal.

Perhaps what most critics aroused in Kamal Sebti's poetry was the poetic performance contrary to the prevailing Arab states, and his attempt to diversify his performance in his long poetic texts, which made it a technical necessity in harmony with the poetic saying. A land of knowledge (77), and since modernity is a distinctive form of Western civilization that opposes the formula of tradition in other cultures, it imposes itself as a homogeneous unit, radiating a world imposed by geographical and symbolic diversity and resonating with the poet's saying (78). He was not a weakness driven by fear of wading into life. Rather, it was an outpouring of vitality that drove its companions to an ideal world, with which they would no longer hate what was around them of the world of people and were narrowed by it. " (79) He relied a lot on the mystical dimension, so he clung to the meaning of martyrdom in poetry. Asceticism, as he wrote poetry ((An Arabist tasteful study of heritage ... in him and his poems were mixed with the characteristics of a Sufi and a fortune teller, and he tried to play with words without expecting him in return for his modernist game)) (80), which is an endeavor among poets since ancient times, as the pre-Islamic poet was ((A person desires life in death, and sees death in life)) (81). Likewise, marginalization and absenteeism prolonged Sabbatarian perfection, as the poet complained in his penultimate (permanent) return to Iraq of human marginalization, and was distressed by his old friends, and because of that, he abhorred friendship and went looking for a utopia with no friends or worries, but nothing from memories (82) The poet chose what was written for him to be a lonely stranger who suffers from his alienation without the poems of others. Rather, he did not try to fuse with a loud, dynamic society, so he folded away from the Iraqi and Dutch people and society, pondering his steps and realizing his project in Europe amidst the congestion of European thought, and touching the fruits of his approach closely, His works were translated into many languages (83), and he was celebrated in the Dutch city of The Hague - not in Baghdad - in 2003 (84), and the world filled with the writings of critics about him (85).

2. Eternal Alienation:

Just as the two poets weaved silently and quietly, their death was also shrouded in silence. Aqil Ali died on May 15 2005 in Baghdad, and he left it quietly that surpassed his silence in his life, but far surpassed him (86). This time, he mixed with his western location, as he found a deceased on his computer chair on 4/22/2006, and his death was discovered by his brother in America who used to call several times without finding an answer, which generated suspicion in himself, so he contacted Kamal Sebti's friend (Yana) She was in Belgium, so she came to the Netherlands and found the poet of Nasiriyah - accompanied by the city police - among his papers, poems and his computer, as he died without anyone knowing about him for more than five days and it was said ten (87).

It seems that Kamal Sabti received some attention after his departure, as President Jalal Talabani ensured that the body was transported to Iraq in fulfillment of the writers of Iraq and their efforts. He passed by the city center and the dean of the poets (Haboubi) gave him a farewell look, in addition to holding a poetic memorial party befitting him.

Arab critics and writers refrained from their obituary except for the effect of loyalty and impartiality in its affiliation, and preferred poetry over loyalty (88), and the departure of the poets did not raise anything in the great scientific edifice of the city (Dhi Qar University and other Iraqi universities), and none of those who counted among the poets initiated anything. Or they join the critics by remembering them and doing what suits their cultural achievement.

Conclusion:

After this journey in the poets' lives, their sociological conditions, and their self-estrangement, the research had to reach specific results, including:

- 1- Aqil Ali represented a new style in the contemporary poem, through its mediation, he was able to express a special grouch that reflects a glowing and renewed thought, for it is a productive traumatism, breaking the restrictions, specifications and restrictive means of commitment, so he broke the restrictions and barriers and came up with a poetic image in a way that he wanted to bring the stranger and was not entrenched in the mind The recipient and his taste is not his potential and strangeness.
- 2- Kamal Sebti demonstrated the possibility of diversity and dealing with modernity in a manner of dialogue close to the recipient who does not deviate much from the global modernist achievement in poetic performance contrary to the prevailing Arab, and his attempt to diversify his performance in his long poetic texts, which became an artistic necessity in harmony with the poetic saying, he seeks And behind him the poet drew the performance classes from moving between the frontiers and free play, especially after his migration to Europe, with the presence of religious, literary, ideological, mythological, popular and historical references on which he leans on to enrich his

poetic experience as a result of his representation of many experiences related to characters, events and places.

- 3- The two poets lived clearly sociological alienation and spatial alienation, whether that was in Nasiriyah, Baghdad or Europe, which was reflected in their poetic texts, as societal marginalization was one of the issues that bound them and affected them clearly in their epistemological achievement.
- 4- The two poets have achieved a great achievement by transferring the seventieth Iraqi culture to Europe, especially as their poetry collections have been translated into other languages.

Margins:

- 1- See: The Poetic Mind 1 / 10-11.
- 2- See: Diwan Al-Nasiri - Abdel-Qader Rasheed: 3/54.
- 3- See: the literary movement in the city of Nasiriyah: 65.
- 4- See: the same source: 64-65.
- 5- Rain and eyes collapsing from his clouds: 12.
- 6- Aqeel Ali: The mystery of the bird that has gone into hiding: 13, and looks: another bird that has disappeared: Introduction
- 7- Another Bird Murring: 22
- 8- The Quranic Significance according to Al-Sharif Al-Murtada: 185
- 9- Rain and eyes darken from its clouds: 11.
- 11- Look: What is left of the Elag: 13.
- 12- Sees: Aqeel Ali: The Mystery of the Faded Bird: 13.
- 13- Consider: Alienation in the life and poetry of Sharif Al-Radhi: 181
- 14- See: Same source: 180
- The Adam Gardens: 57
- 16- Modernity discourse in literature (origins and reference): 321.
- 17- The language of modern poetry in Iraq: 143.
- 18- Poetry and History: 34.
- 19- See: The same source: 34.
- 20- Aqeel Ali: The Mystery of the Lost Bird 13.
- 21- Another Bird Murring: 10
- 22- Poetry and Recitation (Critical Studies): 84
- 23- See: Poetry and Recitation (Critical Studies): 85.
- 24- See: Linguistics Lectures on Semantics: 176.
- 25 - See: Aqeel Ali - the mystery of the bird who has disappeared: 13 The poet did not study except to the extent of the witness and the argument within the generation of the seventies. Looks: Narrative structures in the poetry of the Iraqi seventies: 47, 58 and other places- See: The Tramps Poets of the Pre-Islamic Era: 117.
- 26- Same source.
- 27- See: Aqeel Ali - The Recovered Poet: 12.
- 28- Aqeel Ali: The Mystery of the Lost Bird: 13.
- 29- Same source: 13.
- 30- Aqeel Ali: The Mystery of the Lost Bird: 13.
- 31- See: the same source: 13.
- 32- Aqeel Ali: The Mystery of the Lost Bird: 13.
- 33- Same source: 13.
- 34- Same source: 13.
- 35 Ibid: 13.
- 36 Ibid: 13.
- 37- An interview with the brother of the poet Kamal Sebti, Mr. Ibrahim, on 18/8/2017 at ten o'clock in the evening at his home.
- 38- See: A small sea rose for the spirit of sabbatical perfection: 12.
- 39- Wise Without Cities: 103, see 93, 151.
- 40- Alienation in the life and poetry of Sharif Al-Radhi: 10
- 41- Meeting the poet's brother.
- 42- Sea Rose: 14
- 43- Criticism of poetry in the psychological perspective: 93
- 44- Wise Without Cities: 61
- 45- Alienation in the heritage of the mysticism of Islam: 19
- 46- Meeting the poet's brother.
- 47- Same source.

- 48- The last holy cities: 10
 49- The Artistic Structure of the War Novel in Iraq: 127
 50- Place and its implications in the poetry of Al-Sayyab: 7
 51- Meeting the poet's brother.
 52- Kamal Sabti (On Visions of Critics and Literary Generations) Ibrahim Sebti, Abd al-Karim Kazim: 142-143.
 53 - See: Wise Without Cities, Killers of Countries: 11.
 54- See: the same source: 11.
 55- Seeing: Just a Celebration of a Great Poet 12.
 56 - He looks: Rain and eyes gather in its clouds: 11.
 57 - Look: A sage without cities, killed by the country: 11.
 58- See: the same source: 11.
 59- See: the same source: 11.
 60- See: the same source: 11.
 61- See: the same source: 11.
 62- Kamal Sabti (On Visions of Critics and Literary Generations): 143.
 63- See: the same source: 143-144.
 64- Singing the poetry of Modernity: 91.
 65- Wise Without Cities: 122.
 66 Ibid: 119
 67- Surah Maryam Verse 12:
 68- See: Wise Without Cities: 116, 119, 120
 69- The religious and heritage implications of Andalusian poetry in the fourth century AH: 69
 70 - Looks: Hakim Without Cities respectively: 30, 31, 51, 55, 64, 66, 116, 118, 119, 120, 124, 127, 137,140
 139, 162, 163.
 See: The last holy cities: 10, 11, 12, 17.
 Seen: Sea Rose: 12, 38, 50, 55,
 Seen: Museum of the Remains of the Family: 11, 13, 14, 19, 25, 34, 149,
 100, 129, 137, 138, 162
 71- Intercession in the poetry of the pioneers: 42-43.
 72 - See: the same source: 60.
 73- A small sea rose for the spirit of the perfection of Sabbati: 12.
 74- A mere celebration of a great poet 12.
 75- See: Same source: 12.
 76- See: Love Song to the perfection of my sabbatical - Some Memories 12.
 77- Looking: Just a Celebration of a Great Poet 12.
 78 Sees Poetic Mind: 1/264.
 79 Romanticism, d. Muhammad Ghunaimi Hilal: 59.
 80- A small sea rose for the spirit of sabbatical perfection: 12.
 81- The seduction of heritage, d. Jaber Asfour: 79.
 82- Sees: A small sea rose for the spirit of sabbatical perfection: 12.
 83- He looks: a small sea rose for the spirit of sabbatical perfection: 12, and see Kamal Sabti (in the visions of critics and literary generations): 143.
 84- Looking: Just a Celebration of a Great Poet: 12
 85- See: A small sea rose for the spirit of sabbatical perfection: 12.
 86- Look: Love Song to the perfection of my sabbatical - some memories -: 12.
 87-- A meeting with the poet's brother and looking: a coffin running parallel to tears of humiliation: 11.
 88- Seen: Love Song to Kamal Sabti - Some Memories -: 0-12.

The poet's brother Kamal Sebti told me, and some writers, the circumstances that accompanied the arrival of the news of the poet's death, as the poet's brother was unable to travel under the circumstances known to everyone. I inform him that the government will secure the arrival of the body of the expatriate Iraqi poet Kamal Sebti, in coordination with the Iraqi embassy in the Netherlands and the brother of the late (Riyadh Sebti) residing in America, I sent the poet an amount of (\$ 300) in bonuses to be published in (Al-Hayat London) newspaper and the (Omani Nizwa) magazine, and this is all that the poet who lived poor in his life and his death, rich in his giving, and I found with the poet three poetry collections that did not see Al-Nour, and his brother sponsored the publication of these collections, and I sincerely invite researchers and critics to search and write about every creator who deserves to be dusted off the pens to write about him, and not to wait for his death as happened to our poets.

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Author Information

Asst. Pro. Dr. Ali Hashim Talab Al Zirejawy
Al-Muthanna University / College of Education for
the Humanities
